

DAMAGE TOLERANCE OF DOUBLE-LAP, MULTI-ROW COMPOSITE BOLTED JOINTS CONTAINING SINGLE MISSING FASTENER

Fujian Zhuang, Puhui Chen*

State Key Laboratory of Mechanics and Control of Mechanical Structures, Nanjing University of
Aeronautics and Astronautics, Nanjing 210016, China

E-mail: phchen@nuaa.edu.cn Website: <http://aero.nuaa.edu.cn/>

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ABSTRACT

The subject of this work is evaluation of the damage tolerance of double-lap, three-column and three-row composite bolted joints containing single missing fastener. Missing fastener is one of the damage scenarios may appear in manufacturing and service and it can cause reductions to the strength of the whole joint structure. A high-efficient explicit finite element model validated effective and accurate by experiments was developed and employed to evaluate the residual strength of multi-row composite bolted joints with single missing fastener. It is shown that the removal of fasteners can cause considerable reductions in joint stiffness, initial significant failure loads and ultimate loads of joints, and lead to a notable growth in bolt-load of bolts in the same column as or in the adjacent column to the missing fastener.

1 INTRODUCTION

Reliable design and analysis of composite bolted joints are crucial to the structural safety of current commercial and military aircrafts with massive usage of composite materials, since connections between primary structural elements are designed as multi-row bolted joints in most cases [1]. Extensive research has been done over the past several decades [2-3]. A wide range of variables which can affect the strength of composite bolted joints have been studied, including material properties [4-5], joint geometry [5-7], clearance [8-11], bolt torque and friction [6, 12], biaxial loading [13], dynamic loading [14], hydrothermal environment [15-16], etc.

Unfortunately, there are always various defects and damages arising in such multi-row bolted joints, both during initial processing and in service afterwards. For instance, improper hole drilling, poor fastener installation, and missing fasteners may occur in manufacturing [17]. Hole elongation due to repeated load cycling, premature bolt fracture failure due to unexpected initial cracks, and bolt shear failure because of excessively uneven load distribution can occur in service. These defects and damages can change the bolt-hole fits directly and alter the bolt load proportions severely, leading to reductions in the initial failure strength and probably the ultimate strength [9-10].

Since missing fasteners is the most serious case among the defects and damages above, the particular interest of this paper is the effects of missing fasteners on the mechanical behavior of multi-row composite bolted joints. In the open literature, very little research on this topic has been published, except the work of Gray et al. [7, 18]. In reference [7], Gray et al. established a highly efficient user-defined element to analyze the load distribution of large-scale composite bolted structures with missing fasteners. It was indicated that bolts around the missing fasteners would bear higher loads than those in the pristine cases, but no evidence of effects of missing fasteners on stiffness and strength was presented. Later, an experimental investigation into missing fastener effect in single-lap, triple-row and triple-column composite joints with countersunk bolts was carried out in [18]. The results revealed that missing fasteners could cause distinct losses in load-carrying capacity (up to 11.4%) and, raise the loads of bolts nearby and in the same column. On the contrary, the joint stiffness did not show obvious change, which is however not quite convinced because the coefficient of variation in the control cases was somewhat high. In addition, Gray et al. pointed out that the method of acquiring bolt load distribution from surface strains might bring some inaccuracy in such single-lap countersunk joints, so

the experimental results could not precisely illustrate the effect of missing fasteners on load distribution in a quantitative way.

Besides, the virtual testing analysis method is playing an increasingly important role in aircraft structure design and certification [19]. Numerical models validated by small-scale experiments can be used to predict the behavior of large-scale structures under various load cases. Therefore, in this paper, the effects of missing fasteners is investigated via virtual testing based on a reliable explicit finite element (FE) model, avoiding high expense of multi-row composite bolted joint specimens. The model was validated through comparison with experimental data from literature. Moreover, double-lap, multi-row joints with protruding-head bolts are chosen as the baseline structure. Meanwhile, it becomes possible to achieve an accurate prediction of joint strength using a simple finite element model based on plane stress elements [20-22], without building a complicated and time-consuming model in countersunk situations [23].

In the virtual tests, 3-column and 3-row composite bolted joints with different positions of missing fasteners were designed, referring to the benchmark tests [9] in BOJCAS [24]. Then the mechanical characteristics of the joints under quasi-static tensile loads were analyzed by the FE model. Afterwards, based on the testing results, the effects of missing fasteners on the joint stiffness, load distribution, initial significant failure load and ultimate failure load were discussed quantitatively. Finally, some remarks were concluded as references for composite bolted joint design.

2 PROBLEM DESCRIPTION

The structures under investigation in this article are multi-row bolted joints in double-lap configuration with protruding-head bolts derived from [9]. The geometry dimension and bolt numbering are shown in Figure 1. The bolts used were made of titanium alloy and torqued to 0.5 Nm which represent a finger-tightened condition. Steel washers were arranged on both the nut and head side. Net-fit tolerance was used between bolts and holes, where the nominal clearance is $0\mu\text{m}$, but the possible range in reality is $-2\mu\text{m}\sim 22\mu\text{m}$ according to reamer/bolt sizes [8]. The laminates were manufactured from a carbon fiber/epoxy matrix system (HTA/6376), and had balanced, symmetric and quasi-isotropic lay-ups: $[45/0/-45/90]_{4s}$ for the skin plates, and $[45/0/-45/90]_{2s}$ for the splice plates. Nominal ply thickness was 0.13mm, resulting in the laminate thickness shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Geometry of MFJ9-0 pristine joints with bolt numbering

To investigate the influence of missing fasteners in different positions, all possible conditions were considered. The virtual testing matrix is illustrated in Table 1, including case codes ('MFJ' stands for 'Missing Fastener Joint') and the corresponding bolt numbers of missing fasteners. Pristine joint MFJ9-0 were designed as control cases for comparison with joints containing missing fasteners. All the joints were subjected to quasi-static tensile loading until the ultimate failure in virtual tests.

Case code	Bolt number of the missing fastener
MFJ9-0	--
MFJ9-1	Bolt 1
MFJ9-2	Bolt 2
MFJ9-3	Bolt 3
MFJ9-4	Bolt 4
MFJ9-5	Bolt 5
MFJ9-6	Bolt 6

Table 1: Virtual testing matrix

3 VIRTUAL TESTING SET UP

3.1 Finite element model

All the finite element models of the joints in the paper were built in the ABAQUS/CAE. The 9-bolt pristine joint model is illustrated in Figure 2 and the others are alike. Since these joints are symmetric in the thickness direction, only a half of them were modelled. The washers, nut and bolt shank were integrated as one part as in [10]. The laminates were discretized by SC8R, where only one element was used in the thickness to include all the plies since the laminates are relative thin and largely reduce the cost of analysis. Besides, the bolts were modeled using C3D8R. And the basic material parameters used are shown in Table 2 and 3.

Figure 2: FE model of the pristine 9-bolt joint

E_{11} (GPa)	E_{22} (GPa)	E_{33} (GPa)	G_{12} (GPa)	G_{13} (GPa)	G_{23} (GPa)	$\nu_{12}=\nu_{13}$	ν_{23}	ρ (g·cm ⁻³)
140	10	10	5.2	5.2	3.9	0.3	0.5	1.6
X_T (MPa)	X_C (MPa)	Y_T (MPa)	Y_C (MPa)	Z_T (MPa)	Z_C (MPa)	S_{12} (MPa)	S_{13} (MPa)	S_{23} (MPa)
2200	1600	70	250	50	300	120	120	50

Table 2: Basic material properties of HTA/6376 carbon-epoxy [10]

E (GPa)	ν	ρ (g·cm ⁻³)
110	0.29	4.43

Table 3: Basic material properties of Titanium alloy

ABAQUS/Explicit solver was adopted for higher efficiency and robustness. Unlike the implicit methods used before [10, 12, 20-22, 29], the explicit method provides more stable contact modelling and efficient solution of large structure analyses, as the computational resource needed increases linearly with the growth of model size. Meanwhile, the convergence problem due to strain-softening damage models in implicit FE analyses [10, 29] can be avoided obtaining the ultimate strength of

multi-bolt composite joints [13,19,23].

Boundary and loading conditions can be seen from Figure 2. Grip areas were removed as perfect clamping was assumed there. Symmetric boundary conditions were set at the symmetry planes as shown. The left side of the skin plate was fixed and a prescribed displacement in x direction was applied on the right side of the splice plate to simulate the quasi-static loading. In the explicit models here, a relatively high loading rate (0.2m/s) was used without mass scaling according to Egan [23]. The ratio of kinetic energy to internal energy turned out to be much smaller than 5%, satisfying the requirement of quasi-static analyses.

General contact pairs were arranged between bolt heads and the splice, bolt shanks and holes, as well as the skin and splice. The penalty method was used to carry out both the normal contact behavior and the tangential behavior. The friction coefficient adopted was 0.2 [13]. An initial clearance 10 μ m was used. The finger-tight pre-load (producing a 7.2MPa pressure) was neglected.

3.2 Material damage simulation

The ABAQUS built-in progressive damage model based on the Continuum Damage Mechanics was employed to simulate the initiation and propagation of composite material damage [25] where stiffness degradation was characterized by internal state variables d_i ($i = f, m, s$) [26].

The stress-strain relationship remains linear and the state variables equal to zero before damage onset which is determined by Hashin criteria [27] shown as follows.

Fiber tension ($\hat{\sigma}_{11} \geq 0$):

$$F_{ft} = \left(\frac{\hat{\sigma}_{11}}{X_T} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{\hat{\tau}_{12}}{S_{12}} \right)^2 \quad (1)$$

Fiber compression ($\hat{\sigma}_{11} < 0$):

$$F_{fc} = \left(\frac{\hat{\sigma}_{11}}{X_C} \right)^2 \quad (2)$$

Matrix tension ($\hat{\sigma}_{22} \geq 0$):

$$F_{mt} = \left(\frac{\hat{\sigma}_{22}}{Y_T} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{\hat{\tau}_{12}}{S_{12}} \right)^2 \quad (3)$$

Matrix compression ($\hat{\sigma}_{22} < 0$):

$$F_{mc} = \left(\frac{\hat{\sigma}_{22}}{2S_{23}} \right)^2 + \left[\left(\frac{Y_C}{2S_{23}} \right)^2 - 1 \right] \frac{\hat{\sigma}_{22}}{Y_C} + \left(\frac{\hat{\tau}_{12}}{S_{12}} \right)^2 \quad (4)$$

where, $\hat{\sigma}_{11}$, $\hat{\sigma}_{22}$, $\hat{\tau}_{12}$ are components of the effective stress tensor $\hat{\sigma}$.

Once the onset of damage occurs, the material starts to degrade and the response of material is computed from

$$\boldsymbol{\sigma} = \mathbf{C}_d \boldsymbol{\varepsilon} \quad (5)$$

where, \mathbf{C}_d is the damaged elasticity matrix, which has the form

$$\mathbf{C}_d = \frac{1}{D} \begin{bmatrix} (1-d_f)E_{11} & (1-d_f)(1-d_m)v_{21}E_{22} & 0 \\ (1-d_f)(1-d_m)v_{12}E_{11} & (1-d_m)E_{22} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & (1-d_s)G_{12}D \end{bmatrix} \quad (6)$$

In formula (6), $D=1-(1-d_f)(1-d_m)\nu_{12}\nu_{21}$. d_f , d_m and d_s are damage variables of fiber damage, matrix damage and shear damage respectively [26]. They are derived from damage variables d_f^t , d_f^c , d_m^t and d_m^c which are corresponding to the four failure modes mentioned above, as follows.

$$d_f = \begin{cases} d_f^t & \text{if } \hat{\sigma}_{11} \geq 0 \\ d_f^c & \text{if } \hat{\sigma}_{11} < 0 \end{cases} \quad (7)$$

$$d_m = \begin{cases} d_m^t & \text{if } \hat{\sigma}_{22} \geq 0 \\ d_m^c & \text{if } \hat{\sigma}_{22} < 0 \end{cases} \quad (8)$$

$$d_s = 1 - (1-d_f^t)(1-d_f^c)(1-d_m^t)(1-d_m^c) \quad (9)$$

The degradation law adopted here (② in Figure 3) is a mixed of constant-based instantaneous degradation (① in Figure3) and energy-based gradual degradation (③ in Figure3) models which are both widely used in academic research [28]. It has an initial linear gradual degradation stage as ③ characterized by the input fracture energies and a residual stiffness stage as ① characterized by a maximum degradation constant. Since the second stage with residual stiffness also produces energy dissipation, the fracture energies used (shown in Table 4) for the first stage here are lower than the energies of the same material in other literature [30]. So that the model can account for the sharp decrease in the beginning stage due to the brittle nature of fibers and matrix, as well as the residual strength when the material is subject to compression around the holes [29]. And the residual stiffness is fulfilled by setting an upper bound to damage variables, 0.95 in this paper.

Figure 3: Schematic diagram for material stiffness degradation models

Longitudinal Tensile Fracture Energy (N/mm)	Longitudinal Compression Fracture Energy (N/mm)	Transverse Tensile Fracture Energy (N/mm)	Transverse Compression Fracture Energy (N/mm)
10	7.5	0.1	0.2

Table 4 : Fracture energies for energy-based gradual degradation stage

3.3 Model validation

The model was validated through comparison with experimental data of a similar 3-bolt joint [9, 10], from four aspects, including load displacement characteristics, surface strain, load distribution and failure loads.

3.3.1 Load displacement characteristics

In the experiment, the relative displacement between free ends of skin and splice plates shown in Figure 4 was measured by displacement gauges. And the same positions were used in the simulation for output. Load-relative displacement curves from the experiment and the simulation are shown in Figure 5. As can be seen, the model produces a fairly good coincidence with the experiment.

Figure 4: Locations of measuring points for relative displacement

Figure 5: Load-relative displacement curves from the experiment and the simulation

3.3.2 Surface strain

Two rows of strain gauges were placed between bolts on the surface of the splice plate to obtain forces in the local sections and, furthermore, the load distribution. Figure 6 illustrates the layout of strain gauges arrangement. Figure 7 shows the strain-load curves from the experiment and the simulation. At the beginning, strains in all positions increase along with the applied load. After damage onset, most strains experienced a fluctuation and some even decrease. And results from the simulation are quite consistent with experimental data over these two periods.

Figure 6: Layout of strain gauges arrangement

Figure 7: Strain-load curves from the experiment and the simulation: a) the 1st row, b) the 2nd row

3.3.3 Load distribution and failure loads

Bolt loads were attained directly by extracting CFT (total force due to contact pressure and frictional stress) between each bolt and its corresponding hole along the loading direction. Figure 8 shows the bolt load distribution from the experiment and the simulation. Initial linear behavior can be seen from both cases and bolt load proportions were extracted in this phase. Then, a significant oscillation occurs because of bearing failure at holes 1 and 3, which is marked as “initial significant failure event” in Figure 8. Afterwards, bolt loads even out until the “ultimate failure event” due to net tension failure at holes 1 or 3. Table 5 shows the bolt load proportions and failure loads from the experiment and the simulation. As can be seen, the model is capable of predicting the load distribution and failure loads satisfactorily with errors below 4%.

Figure 8: Bolt load distribution: a) experiment, b) simulation

	Bolt load proportions			Failure loads	
	Bolt 1	Bolt 2	Bolt 3	Initial significant failure	Ultimate failure
Experimental results	35.4%	26.1%	38.1%	49.5 kN	69.8 kN
Simulation results	36.4%	26.0%	36.7%	48.2 kN	67.9 kN
Error	2.8%	0.4%	3.7%	2.6%	2.7%

Table 5: Bolt load proportions and failure loads from the experiment and the simulation

Overall, with comparison to the experiment, the model can predict the mechanical behavior of the multi-row joint effectively and satisfactorily, and was thus adopted to investigate the effects of missing fasteners on the mechanical characteristics.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1 Residual joint stiffness and failure loads

The load-displacement curves of MFJ9- i ($i=0\sim6$) are illustrated in Figure 9. Typically, they consist of three stages: (i) linear, (ii) damaged and (iii) post-failure, where the stiffness of the damaged stage is much lower than that of the linear stage. And the joint stiffness and failure loads are summarized in Table 6.

Figure 9: Load-displacement curves of MFJ9- i series ($i = 0\sim6$)

	Joint Stiffness		Initial significant failure load		Ultimate failure load	
	Value (kN/mm)	Percentage difference from pristine case	Value (kN)	Percentage difference from pristine case	Value (kN)	Percentage difference from pristine case
MFJ9-0	152.7	--	152.4	--	210.0	--
MFJ9-1	145.9	-4.5%	127.6	-16.3%	193.2	-8.0%
MFJ9-2	149.9	-1.8%	126.2	-17.2%	194.1	-7.6%
MFJ9-3	145.9	-4.5%	125.6	-17.6%	195.1	-7.1%
MFJ9-4	147.6	-3.3%	128.9	-15.4%	203.2	-3.2%
MFJ9-5	150.6	-1.4%	133.0	-12.7%	206.2	-1.8%
MFJ9-6	147.7	-3.3%	130.9	-14.1%	204.9	-2.4%

Table 6: Joint stiffness and failure loads results

It is shown that the removal of fasteners can reduce the joint stiffness. The magnitudes of reduction can be up to 4.5%. And missing fasteners in the outside rows (row 1 and 3) lead to larger loss in stiffness than those in the inside row (row 2). Besides, missing fasteners in the outside column 1 (MFJ9-1, 2, 3) cause slightly larger losses in stiffness than the corresponding ones in the inside column 2 (MFJ9-4, 5, 6).

In terms of the initial significant failure load, a considerable reduction can be seen and the maximum magnitudes are 17.2%. These declines are directly related to changes of the maximum bolt loads (marked as P_{Bmax}) due to missing fasteners because bearing damage in the hole with P_{Bmax} basically indicates the initial significant failure event. The row and column effects are not as clear as those in joint stiffness.

On the ultimate failure load, missing fasteners can result in large reductions with the max to 8.0%. The reason is bolt missing in multi-column joints can lead to uneven load transferring in the width direction between columns. For example, figure 10 shows the effect of missing fastener in column 1 on the final failure pattern. In MFJ9-3, fiber tensile damage in column 1 is not as much as that in column 2 and 3, which is the result of the unevenness of load transferring. It means that, when

laminates in column 2 and 3 reach their ultimate strength, laminate in column 1 does not, but the load-bearing capability of the whole joint has already come up to the top.

Figure 10: Final fiber tension failure pattern of MFJ9-0 and MFJ9-3 (max of the envelop)

Finally, it is apparent that, in most cases for multi-column joints, missing fasteners in the outside rows or columns can reduce the ultimate failure loads in a greater amplitude than those in the inside.

4.2 Changes of load distribution

To investigate the effects of missing fasteners on the load distribution, bolt load proportions in the linear stage were extracted as shown in Table 7. The values with underlines are the maximum bolt load proportions in each case.

Case code	Bolt1	Bolt2	Bolt3	Bolt4	Bolt5	Bolt6	Bolt7	Bolt8	Bolt9
MFJ9-0	<u>12.5%</u>	9.1%	12.4%	11.7%	8.2%	11.7%	12.4%	9.1%	12.5%
MFJ9-1	0	14.3%	<u>14.6%</u>	13.4%	9.5%	12.7%	12.7%	9.3%	12.9%
MFJ9-2	<u>15.5%</u>	0	15.4%	12.5%	9.0%	12.6%	12.7%	9.1%	12.7%
MFJ9-3	<u>14.7%</u>	14.2%	0	12.7%	9.4%	13.4%	13.0%	9.3%	12.6%
MFJ9-4	<u>13.9%</u>	10.3%	13.2%	0	11.6%	13.0%	13.9%	10.2%	13.3%
MFJ9-5	13.2%	9.7%	13.1%	13.6%	0	<u>13.7%</u>	13.1%	9.8%	13.1%
MFJ9-6	13.4%	10.3%	<u>13.8%</u>	13.0%	11.6%	0	13.3%	10.3%	13.8%

Table 7: Bolt load proportions of MFJ9-i series

Bolt loads in each column of MFJ9-0 present a “bathtub distribution”, which means the bolt loads are larger in outside rows than in inside rows. Meantime, bolts in outside columns also carry more loads than the ones in the inside column. This may explain the row and column effect in joint stiffness and ultimate strength.

By examining the results in Table 7, we can see an increase in all the load proportions of bolts remained in joints with missing fastener, comparing to the pristine cases. The changes were summarized in Figure 11 in an intuitive way. It is shown that the maximum changes occurred in bolts closest to and in the same column with the missing fastener hole, followed by the other bolts in the same column or the bolts in the adjacent column. The maximum changes in bolt load proportions are 5.2%. Additionally, the extents of bolt load changes depend on the position of missing fasteners. The bolts removed in the outer columns and/or rows, which carry more loads in the pristine joints, will result in larger variations than those in the inner.

Figure 11: Changes of bolt load proportions in MFJ9-*i* series

5. CONCLUSIONS

The effects of missing fasteners on the global joint stiffness, initial significant failure load, ultimate failure load and bolt load distribution in 3-row and 3-column, double-lap composite bolted joints were investigated. Firstly, a high-efficient explicit finite element model with capability of progressive damage analysis was developed and validated. Then, virtual tests on joints with various positions of missing fasteners were conducted. By comparison between results of pristine joints and joints with missing fasteners, the following remarks were concluded:

- (1) Missing fasteners can reduce the global joint stiffness.
- (2) In terms of the ultimate load, missing fasteners can lead to significant decreases in multi-column joints. The reason is missing bolt in multi-column joints is able to cause uneven load transferring between different columns.
- (3) In joints with missing fasteners, bolts in the same column as or in the adjacent column to the missing one experience a significant increase in load.
- (4) Fasteners in outside rows or columns have larger influence on the joint stiffness, ultimate strength and load distribution than the inner ones when they are removed. It is because bolts in the outside rows and columns carry more loads in the pristine joints according to the load distribution analysis.
- (5) Missing fasteners can also raise the maximum bolt load proportions in a notable scale, leading to relevant and considerable reductions in the initial significant failure loads which may be important for limit load design.

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